

Factsheet

trans4num Hungarian NBS site conducts experiments in three replications comparing different NBS innovations with conventional intensive farming systems. An important output of the NBS site will be minimising the negative environmental impacts of the agricultural production and generating evidence for integrating NBS in national and local policies.

	<p>Landscape formation in the Szigetköz region</p> <p>It is important to understand landscape formation to continue the efficient planning of agriculture measures.</p>	<p>Zoltán Fűzfa presenting the history of the Szigetköz region landscape and its importance for agriculture</p> <p>Landscape in the Szigetköz region</p>
	<p>Agriculture of the Szigetköz region</p> <p>The largest European alluvial plain, Szigetköz is a region of significant agricultural activity having both small and large-scale farmers.</p>	<p>Dr. András Vér presenting the agriculture of the Szigetköz region and the challenges faced.</p> <p>Agriculture in the Szigetköz region</p>
	<p>NBS test site</p> <p>The experiments conducted on the site lead to the potential adoption of innovative approaches for traditional practices.</p>	<p>Viktória Vona presenting the Hungarian NBS test site and the experiments to be conducted.</p> <p>NBS test site in Hungary</p>

Funded by the European Union

trans4num is a four-year project funded under the Zero Pollution call as an EU-China international cooperation action on nature-based solutions (NBS) for nutrient management in agriculture.

trans4num ambition is to broadly enhance the NBS implementation in Europe with an integrative and tested multi-level approach, in dialogue with academic partners, practice partners and societal stakeholders.

<http://trans4num.eu>